

Analyzing Open Government High Value Datasets: Availability, Publishers' Contribution and Technical Specifications

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Abstract. Extracting value from open (government) data has been in the limelight for quite some time now, with the Open Government Data (OGD)-also referred to as the Public Sector Information (PSI)- Directive, emphasizing the need for discovery of potential related to PSI and the re-use of data. This study provides insight on high-value datasets (HVD), i.e., the OGD matching the rigorous quality standards in terms of particularly the completeness, timeliness, and machine-processability, in the European Data Portal (EDP) in order to measure various aspects of the datasets, which will help obtain further insights on the current availability status, potential interoperability possibilities, drivers and barriers. The rationale behind this approach is to identify HVD in line with the thematic categories of the PSI Directive and to put a focus on the EDP HVD across three dimensions, viz., data publishing, availability, and technical requirements which need to be met. Findings attest the need for provisioning qualitatively robust HVDs with requisite technical specifications for facilitating value derivation by the range of stakeholders. Apart from contributing towards the HVD and OGD literature, the study lends insights across the availability-value generation focus via the EDP, thereby providing policy implications and further research pointers along these lines.

Keywords: Open government data · European Data Portal · High value datasets · Technical specifications · Interoperability · Data publishers · Data availability

1 Introduction

Extracting value from open data has been in the limelight for quite some time now, with the Open Government Data (OGD)-also referred to as the Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive [1] emphasizing the need for discovery of potential related to public sector information and the re-use of data. PSI is a rich data source, which can actively assist in the transformation of a plethora of applications in society, politics, economics, legislative bodies, environment, and more. The value of publicly available information

has been pursued through several Open Government Data initiatives (OGDIs), which attempt to deliver benefits and satisfy a set of defined objectives, such as enhanced transparency and accountability, innovation, improved decision-making, stimulation of data re-use, counteracting of corruption, and the provision of new services and products [2].

One of the first associations that come to mind when the term “value” is analyzed, is the one related to economic value, which can be defined as “the worth of a good or service as determined by the market” [3]. However, in the context of open data and the value creation from publicly available information, more dimensions of value are involved, one of them being the social value, which is created when resources, inputs, processes, or policies are combined to generate improvements in the lives of individuals or society as a whole [3]. To complement the aforementioned statements, shared value is based on the idea that societal needs, not only economic needs, define markets [4], so it is a parameter that needs to also be taken into consideration. In other words, public value might include the economic value in the way it was described previously, the social or cultural value which contributes to a society’s well-being and prosperity, the political value which promotes public engagement and collaboration, and/or the ecological value by actively promoting sustainable development [5].

As far as high-value datasets (HVD) are concerned, a HVD, according to the revised PSI Directive [1], is defined as being listed in one of the following six thematic areas: Geospatial, Earth Observation and Environment, Meteorological, Statistical, Companies and company ownership, and Mobility. These thematic areas derive from the analysis conducted in accordance with their potential to generate and promote any of the aforementioned types of value, having significant impact on a large cross-section of society, and having the ability to be combined with other datasets under the same purpose [1].

On a parallel note, data interoperability plays an important role, in its turn, in the creation of value, since the public sector information rendered available for re-use needs to meet a number of quality criteria which potentially affect the data discoverability, availability, machine readability and accessibility. Interoperability is the key, and, in order to facilitate data re-use, it needs to be ensured through a series of requirements regarding the data format, processing, machine readability, relevant metadata and other principles [1]. Data interoperability, from a semantic, i.e., lending interpretation and sense-making to the datasets sourced from multitudinous and diverse sources [6] and technical, i.e., standardization and homogenization of the diverse technological foundations across the sources not only in terms of communication as well as the information exchanged across the communication channels [7] viewpoint, can act as a technical or operational enabler for data re-use [8]. Vis-a-vis the specific case of e-government, interoperability across the three levels, viz., technical interoperability in terms of the communication details at different levels of the government; semantic interoperability in terms of the interpretative implications of information; and, organizational interoperability in terms of the implications of information exchange for the recipient, needs to take into cognizance the infrastructures and connectedness [9–13]. Extrapolating these e-government interoperability cases to the OGD context, it falls in place to ascertain the way technical aspects of HVD are conducive for value derivation by the stakeholders, in the long-run.

With this background, this study provides insights on HVD, i.e., the OGD matching the rigorous quality standards in terms of particularly the completeness, timeliness, and machine-processability [14–16], in the European Data Portal in order to measure various aspects of the datasets, such as their availability, information about the publishers which provide the datasets, and technical specifications which will help gain further insight on potential interoperability hinders and more. The main research goal of the presented study is to identify HVD according to the thematic categories of the PSI Directive (as mentioned previously), and to retrieve the datasets from the European Data Portal to examine aspects of them linked to them, more specifically, focusing on the three dimensions of data availability, data publishers' contribution, and the technical specifications. Further insights on data interoperability, and other aspects of data quality are also indirectly targeted due to their close proximity to the topic but also emerging importance.

The remaining article is organized as follows: in the Background section, an overview of the literature regarding HVD and the proportional importance of technical specifications of data will be presented, while the Research Method section contains the description of the proposed methodological approach. The Results section consists of the data analysis and findings of the applied method, the Discussion section includes the interpretation of the findings in a meaningful context, while the Future Directions section explains the limitations of the presented study and potential ways this research could be expanded and replicated in various other implementations in the future.

2 Background

In general, value (or social welfare) is conceptualized as an aggregate measure of social and economic value [17]. The two types of value frequently discussed, as mentioned previously, are the economic (related to the worth of a product or service determined by the market) and the social value (related to the advancements and improvements in society or the individual) [17]. Benington and Moore [18] gave another dimension to the conventional definition of public value, adding to the economic and social, the cultural and political value. However, determining how OGD can contribute to the generation of those values and how this process can be quantified and measured is a task requiring a number of mechanisms to be put in place in order to achieve it [19]. In this vein, Jetzek and colleagues developed a conceptual model to demonstrate how data can produce value along the four identified mechanisms: Efficiency, Innovation, Transparency and Participation [17]. The conceptual model consists of the enabling factors for value creation, the value generating mechanisms and the impact on economic and social value, as well as the relationships among them, indicated by several analyzed hypotheses. One of the enabling factors presented, especially significant for the present study, is the technical connectivity factor, which refers to all the relevant infrastructure supporting the transfer and circulation of data among the systems of governmental agencies and more. These technologies need to be able to assist with all the tasks related to the handling, processing, visualization, and integration of data, while in parallel, support the structurization of unstructured or semi-structured data, interoperability (mainly semantic in this context), and interconnection between disparate data sources. Semantic technologies, as an integral part of the aforementioned technical connectivity, are at the heart of this construct,

and, according to [17], positively affect efficiency through improved interoperability and innovation by proposing new methods and ways to analyze and transform data.

As far as the benefits of an Open Government Data Initiative (OGDI) are concerned, various studies have examined their parameters and the way they interact. In this light, the findings of a conducted study by [2] showed that the majority of benefits delivered by implemented OGDIs are of operational or technical nature, at a next phase, of economic and, lastly, of societal nature, the latter being the toughest to measure. The technical and operational benefits are closely linked to the technical connectivity mentioned previously and, among others, they include easier access to data, better data discoverability, data reuse and improved decision-making by managing to compare data from disparate sources [2]. In this light, it becomes clear that the technical dimension of available datasets in the portal is a dimension which needs to be included in any analysis aiming to bring forth conclusions regarding interoperability, technical connectivity, or the creation of value through improved technical and semantic means.

Before moving on to the specified Methodology of the presented study, it is noteworthy to go through the existing literature on HVD and open government data in order to better understand the context of this research, as well as mentioned conducted research on interoperability and open government data, as a critical dimension which needs to be considered when talking about data and value.

2.1 Related Research on HVD with Reference to OGD

In sharp contradistinction to Big Data, HVD is not all about the volume but a juxtaposition of volume with quality metrics, such as, completeness, machine-processability, granularity, accessibility, timeliness, non-discriminatory and license-free [20]. Table 1 presents a snapshot of the HVD-OGDs studies, and it may be inferred that as such, specific focus on the HVD is few and far between.

2.2 Related Research on Interoperability with Reference to Open Government Data

In its crudest terms, interoperability is defined as the exchange of data and services across a network of distributed systems [32, 33]. Utility of interoperability of OGD has been underscored in a plethora of literature with specific reference to the interoperability dimensions: semantic (commonality of understanding among the data/services exchange parties to draw congruent inferences), syntactic (arriving at common schemas, sequence and arrangement of terms representing an entity), technical (covers a gamut of aspects like compatibility of technologies and systems in place as well as their open/closed nature and scope defining their formal and rigorous descriptions), operational (attaining interoperability between and among actors, the ones engaged in data sharing protocols) and organizational (compatibility between cross-border organizational systems in terms of processes, formats and entities) [32–35]. Whilst most of the studies hint at the theoretical value and implications of OGD interoperability [17, 36–39], as such, the research on OGD interoperability with empirical investigations is evolving. For instance, an RDF schema vocabulary is designed and validated for facilitating linkages amongst the OGD given their disparate and granular nature [40]. Likewise, in another instance,

a framework of ontological interoperability of the real-time OGD was validated in the Iranian energy sector [41]. A comprehensive open-source portal for OGD interoperability is also available via the Tetherless World Constellation (TWC)'s Linking Open Government Data (LOGD) portal which is based on providing solutions to semantic interoperability [42]. In another context of Uppsala, Sweden, the empirical study on the interoperability of OGD for Green IoT (Internet of Things) is being empirically validated [39]. A sophisticated Delivering Information of Government (DIGO) platform was designed for facilitating OGD interoperability across the Swedish OGD portal and validated with mashup applications and data fusion on linked open data (LOD) cloud [43].

Another cause of concern is to produce interoperable OGD-thanks to the unique RDF (Resource Description Framework) vocabularies for creating the triplet sets alongside the relational OGD, i.e., OLAP (Online Analytical Processing) data cubes [44]- and the same is possible via ontological interoperability algorithms-case in point being the OGD portal of Iran and the ancillary data management system [45]. Similar conclusions were derived in regard to the conflicts pertaining to the structural (consequence of the different practices of modeling the structure of the OGD) and naming (the usage of different Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs)) facets, viz. Complexities pertaining to the measurement unit; gender; temporality; parametric measurements; measures' selection; and hierarchical levels, which were empirically validated across six OGD portals covering Scotland, UK, Belgium, Japan, Italy and Ireland [46]. Similarly, drawing inferences from the case studies of Belgian air quality sensor data and the railway infrastructure data, it was shown that linked time series approach is feasible for sustainability of OGD interoperability and availability on account of data storage via improvised caching strategy which reduces the web server's CPU (Central Processing Unit) load, publishing cost and the requirement for client-server interaction [47]. Interoperability was a challenge in the US OGD given the differentials in compatibility of the portals between the legislative and executive branches of the government [48].

Having taken into consideration the extended background presented in this Section, the methodological approach for the conducted study is defined and tailored to fit the purpose of this research, which is to provide information useful regarding the 6 thematic categories of HVD in the European Data Portal, against a number of defined criteria related to their availability, interoperability and further technical details.

Table 1. Major studies identifying HVD and OGD.

Excerpt	Author/s	Inferences regarding HVD-OGDs
“High-value information is information that can be used to increase agency accountability and responsiveness; improve public knowledge of the agency and its operations; further the core mission of the agency; create economic opportunity; or respond to need and demand as identified through public consultation” (p. 2495)	[21] [22] [23] [24]	This definition was provided by Office of Management and Budget, US (OMB, 2009: pp. 7); OGD is also referred to as Public Sector Information (PSI) and the study refers to “High-value information” as being congruent to HVD
A reference to the high value datasets for statistical analysis	[25]	OGD-HVD dimension needs to be meticulously approached
High value creation potential of OGD is being referred	[26]	Value creation assessment framework does not necessarily refer to the HVD trait of OGD
There is a linkage between HVD and timely availability of the same	[27]	Given the lack of accessibility of HVD via the UK OGD portals, interoperability of lesser value OGD result in incoherent analyses
Geospatial OGD across French municipality were HVD	[28]	This calls for attention of researchers to understand why OGD-HVD is sparse and niche
“... calling attention to a set of unanswered questions about the governance issues around data release: who should decide what data is “high value” and how do they choose? How does a user know when data is fit for re-use, how does a user know what has been done to that data, and what restrictions govern its use?”	[29]	Given the authors’ impetus on creating a OGD ecosystem, it is warranted that such ecosystemic approach be built on the edifice of OGD-HVD
Tracing the evolution of OGD initiative in the US, the authors mention of how the Obama government issued directives for publishing of HVDs with a caveat that it is the issuing public authority which will decide what’s HVD	[30]	US OGD portal needs to be taken up in further studies to assess the provisioning of HVD-OGD after more than two decades now
There is a mismatch between the HVD and the extent to which public authority is accountable for its being HVD as far as the US is concerned	[31]	This raises the question regarding the extent to which the transparency-accountability conjunction is realized in practice in the US, thereby, providing a line of further research

3 Research Method

This section aims to describe the research method adopted in the current study. The intended outcome of this methodology is to analyze datasets retrieved from the European Data Portal (EDP) against a defined set of requirements in order to consider the following three dimensions, while in parallel, the categories of HVD as specified by the PSI Directive are kept in mind: i) the dataset's availability, ii) the dataset's publishing authorities and entities, and iii) the dataset's technical specifications. The retrieval of datasets from the EDP is conducted by applying the following filters in the Quick Search menu:

1. **Categories** (as defined by the PSI Directive):

- Geospatial
- Earth Observation and Environment
- Meteorological
- Statistical
- Companies and company ownership
- Mobility

2. **Metadata quality** (Scoring: Sufficient)

3. **Format:** All available

4. **Data services:** YES

The first filter, which is about the dataset category, is specified so as to include the HVD thematic categories defined by the PSI Directive. The second filter about the metadata quality is set to "sufficient", which is the minimum, in order to allow for as many datasets as possible and to give us the opportunity to later put focus on the datasets' technical aspects when these are not considered optimal (due to metadata being one of the most important parameters to consider in this case). The same reasoning applies for the data format. The last filter, "Data services", is the filter which allows for the identification of real-time or close to real-time data. The EDP mentions that with this filter active, the datasets returned are datasets which are used in at least one data service, something that clearly implies the data is real-time or close to real-time, as the data service stream is constantly available. This filter is very important in the presented study, as it is one of the few indicators applicable to determine whether a dataset is considered high value. Real-time/close to real-time data is closely associated with high value [49, 50], however, it is an indicator which can work in conjunction with other indicators of HVD.

Regarding the first filter in the Quick Search, it is worth noting that some high-value datasets may fit into numerous categories on the EDP, and the categories listed are not exhaustive. These categories are not mutually exclusive; some datasets may fall into multiple categories. The mapping between the 6 thematic categories of HVD and the equivalent available categories in the EU Data Portal are shown in Table 2. In line with the aforesaid, the authors aim to provide insight on the following three dimensions:

- Availability
- Publisher/s
- Technical specifications

Table 2. The mapping between the PSI Directive thematic categories for HVD and the EDP search categories.

PSI Directive HVD Thematic Categories	European Data Portal (EDP) Categories
Geospatial	Regions and cities
Earth Observation and Environment	Energy, Forestry and food, Fisheries, Agriculture
Meteorological	Environment
Statistical	Education, Culture and sport, Health, Population and society, Justice, Legal system and public safety, Science and technology, international issues, Government, and public sector
Companies and company ownership	Economy and finance
Mobility	Transport

As a metric for data availability, the number of openly available datasets per category (as defined earlier) will be considered. This will help the authors to gain some insight on the comparison for availability among the HVD categories. The second dimension, which concerns the data publisher, is considered in order to examine elements regarding the distribution of these data sources, the most active contributors of datasets and other intuitive information. The last dimension of technical specifications is an approach for data interoperability, considering that technical specifications such as available data formats, machine-readability, metadata quality, available APIs (Application Programming Interfaces), documentation, and licensing are factors which directly affect the dataset's technical and semantic interoperability. So, in this case, the analysis framework for the retrieved datasets includes the aforementioned criteria, which are applied in order to draw conclusions regarding how interoperable the HVD are, what insufficiencies exist from a technical point of view, and what could potentially be translated into more specific technical requirements for HVD, in general. The importance of the technical specifications of the available datasets and how interoperability can play a critical role for HVD is also emphasized by the conceptual model by [17], referred to as "technical connectivity" and as one of the dimensions of the conceptual model (the aspect the authors are focusing on in this study), which strengthens the inclusion of this dimension in the proposed approach.

Overall, the methodological steps to achieve the aforementioned steps are described in Fig. 1 starting with the retrieval of the high-value datasets from the EDP having first applied the Quick Search filters with a final examination of the three dimensions of availability, data publisher analysis and technical specifications. In the following Section, the results of the applied methodology and analysis framework are presented and explained in further detail.

Fig. 1. A flowchart of the research methodology.

4 Results

The three-dimensional outcome of the applied methodology is described and analyzed in this Section. These three dimensions are explained first, followed by some general remarks on the analysis results and other derived information of significance within the context of this study's focus.

4.1 Availability

To begin with, the authors initiated the analysis by examining the criterion of the availability of high-value datasets (Table 3).

Table 3. The availability of HVDs and number of publishers per category.

HVD Categories	Geospatial	Earth Observation and Environment	Meteorological	Statistical	Companies and Company Ownership	Mobility
Total number of datasets	523	2	795	73	1426	92
Total number of publishers	17	1	17	15	20	9

The majority of available HVDs come from the category “Companies and company ownership”, followed by “Meteorological” and “Geospatial” data. “Mobility”, “Statistical” and “Earth observation and Environment” come afterwards, with the latter being the category with the fewest datasets. A visual representation of the results is presented in Fig. 2. Apart from the availability of HVDs on the EDP (denoted in blue), Fig. 2 depicts the number of contributing publishers (denoted in red) per HVD thematic category. To gain a deeper understanding of these results, descriptive statistics is applied. The descriptive statistics show that there is a difference among the 6 HVD categories. Based on the established criteria, there were 2,911 high-value datasets (HVDs) identified, and the total number of publishers that contributed data in each distinct category was 79. The number of publishers per category is not the same in number and distinct. For instance, the geospatial HVD dataset category contains 526 datasets published by 17 distinct publishers. Other categories were distinct, but the statistical datasets category is mapped (see Table 2) to Health, Education, Culture and sport, Population and society, International issues, Justice, Legal system and public safety, Government and public sector, Science and technology. Thus, all these subcategories are mentioned with a single label “Statistical” to make the EDP dataset categories and the HVDs categories match successfully. Furthermore, inferential statistics is applied to the number of HVDs and the publishers, and the output of the independent samples t-test is presented in Table 4. T-tests are used to compare the means of two groups to understand if there is any difference between them or not [51, 52] and the method has been applied in different studies veering around interoperability of datasets [53–56]. The independent samples t-test is used for the scenario when we need to compare the number of publishers for each category of the HVDs. For instance, the number of publishers for Geospatial data against the number of publishers for statistical data. Based on the results, the t-value (which is 2.082746) is less than the critical t-value of 2.228139 for a two-tailed t-test at $\alpha = 0.05$. More specifically, the two-tailed p-value is 0.063903, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the means of the two groups. Based on these results, we can say that there is no evidence to suggest that the availability of HVDs is significantly different among the different categories.

Fig. 2. Availability of HVDs on the EDP and the number of publishers per category.

Table 4. Independent samples t-test to compare the means of publishers and number of HVDs per category.

	Categorization of HVDs	Publishers
Mean	485.1667	13.16667
Variance	308101.4	48.96667
Observations	6	6
Pooled Variance	154075.2	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df (degree of freedom)	10	
t Stat (t-value)	2.082746	
P(T < = t) one-tail	0.031951	
t Critical one-tail	1.812461	
P(T < = t) two-tail	0.063903	
t Critical two-tail	2.228139	

4.2 Data Publisher/s

The contributing data publishers in each HVDs category have been extracted from the EDP based on the criteria of search. Figure 3a captures the total number of contributing publishers for the retrieved datasets and the distribution of the publishers and HVD categories. Figure 3a shows the dataset contribution per HVD category for each data publisher. Also, Fig. 3a shows that the Joint Research Centre, for example, has only published two datasets in the Earth observations field, but has published 73 datasets in the meteorological HVD category. This provides strong evidence that publishers are more interested in publishing data in the meteorological HVD category than in the Earth observation field.

The most contributing publishers per HVD category are shown in Fig. 3b, where each HVD category is denoted, again, in a different colour. Interestingly, of all the 79 publishers-contributors, the majority of HVD has been published by the following 15 sources. Among the top data publishers for Geospatial Data are the Statistics Sweden (Statistiska Centralbyrån, SCB), the City of Dresden (Dresden Stadt), the Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology (Sächsisches Landesamt für Umwelt, Landwirtschaft und Geologie), and the State Office for Basic Geoinformation Saxony (GeoSN)/ Landesamt für Geobasisinformation Sachsen (GeoSN). Regarding the Earth Observation and Environment category, there were only 2 datasets available using the proposed filtering and these were offered by the Joint Research Centre. The Statistics Sweden (Statistiska Centralbyrån, SCB), the City of Dresden (Dresden Stadt), the Saxon State Office for Environment, the State Office for Basic Geoinformation Saxony (GeoSN)/ Landesamt für Geobasisinformation Sachsen (GeoSN), and the Joint Research Centre are also the top contributors for the Meteorological category but also for the Mobility category.

Fig. 3a. Contributing data publishers in all the HVDs categories.

Fig. 3b. The top 15 data publishers (contributors) in all the HVD categories.

As far as the category of Companies and company ownership is concerned, the Statistics Sweden (Statistiska Centralbyrån, SCB), the Czech Ministry of Finance (Ministerstvo financí), the EU Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, and the Saxon State Ministry for Regional Development (Sächsisches Staatsministerium für Regionalentwicklung), while for the category of Statistical data (for which some examples of inferential statistics were applied), the top contributors are the European Medicines Agency, the Council of the European Union, and the State Office for Basic Geoinformation Saxony (GeoSN)/ Landesamt für Geobasisinformation Sachsen (GeoSN), the City of Dresden (Dresden Stadt). The latter is not so surprising considering the mapping of the HVD PSI Directive thematic categories to the EDP Search categories. The mapping is not mutually exclusive, which means that various datasets could belong to more than one data category. Interestingly, most contributors for all the HVD categories originate from three countries: Sweden, Germany and the

Czech Republic, while some European Agencies like the Joint Research Centre, the Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy, and other Directorate-Generals are also in the forefront in terms of HVD publishing.

4.3 Technical Specifications

Table 5 shows the “Technical Specifications” vis-a-vis the HVDs identified in the Search protocols (Fig. 1). The rationale behind the selection of those parameters derives from the mandatory technical requirements for HVD set by the European Commission with respect to what should follow the publication and re-use of the datasets [1]. These parameters are necessary to allow for the extraction of insights regarding technical aspects of the available datasets, and, potentially, pave the way towards the elicitation of new technical requirements from a portal’s publisher’s perspective as also from the user’s perspective. As presented on Table 5, most datasets are offered in machine-readable formats, however, the distinction between machine-readable and machine-processable data needs to be referred to. In order to achieve machine-processable information, a number of intermediate steps and sophisticated techniques need to be applied, which is a demanding process, still not supported sufficiently. One would expect this could be different when it comes to HVD, however, this appears not to be the case, so the problem of non-machine-processable data remains. Most datasets are available to download by bulk download options and these datasets are accompanied by SPARQL endpoints.

The majority of the studied datasets are accompanied by appropriate documentation and a license. According to the technical requirements for HVD set by the European Commission, a Creative Commons 4.0 or equivalent license is required. The studied datasets come with their own license type, which can also be data type specific. Some of those licenses include the CC0–1.0 Universal license, data license Germany Zero 2.0, and data license Germany attribution 2.0. As far as the Extensive Metadata parameter is concerned, the EDP follows the DCAT Application Profile (AP) for data portals in Europe (DCAT-AP) [57]. This means that the metadata available needs to be compatible with the equivalent specifications as these are posed by DCAT. In this experiment, the metadata filter was set to “Sufficient”, while there exist two more options of “Good”, and “Excellent”. The DCAT metadata requirements which are not demanded for the “Sufficient” metadata labeling, can be turned into recommendations in order for the publishers to improve the metadata quality before publishing the dataset. As mentioned previously, metadata is one of the most important enablers for the semantic interoperability and reusability of the data, so it is one of the parameters remaining in the limelight.

Table 5. The technical requirements set for high value datasets.

Technical Specifications	Smart Charts/Graphs
Machine-Readable Data	Figure 4 depicts the predominant data formats utilized within the various categories of HVDs. Each category of HVDs employs unique data formats. For instance, geospatial data is primarily distributed in JSON (Java Script Object Notation) format, which surpasses all other formats in terms of usage. Similarly, meteorological data is primarily provided in HTML (HyperText Markup Language) distributions, which exceed all other formats in terms of usage
Machine-Processable Data	Machine-readable information is not necessarily machine processable. This commonly encountered problem remains for HVD
Bulk Download API	Most of the datasets mentioned in this study are available in machine-readable formats and are accompanied by bulk download options. Additionally, these datasets can be accessed and downloaded through APIs and SPARQL endpoints
Extensive Metadata	The metadata quality was set up as “Sufficient” for searching the HVD. For EDP, this is in accordance with the equivalent DCAT (Data Catalog vocabulary) specifications
Marginal Charges Applied	Unavailable Information on the EDP
Publicly Available Documentation	Yes, most of the datasets mentioned in this study are accompanied by publicly available documentation. These datasets can also be found on federated catalogs, national data portals, and ultimately on the EDP. However, the EDP does not explicitly specify the availability of documentation. Available information/documentation may vary from portal to portal
License (CC-4.0 or equivalent license)	Most datasets have their own license type. Notably, the CC0-1.0 Universal license, data license Germany Zero 2.0, and data license Germany Attribution 2.0 are among the licenses predominantly employed

The available data formats for each HVD category (in different colours) are presented in Fig. 4. As presented in the Figure, for the Geospatial, and Companies and company ownership categories, JSON is one of the most commonly available formats, while for Meteorological datasets HTML and TIFF (Tag Image File Format) are dominant. The Statistical category is overrepresented by HTML, CSV (Comma Separated Value) and RDF XML (Resource Description Framework- Extensible Markup Language), while the Mobility Category is mostly available in ESRI (Environmental Systems Research

Institute) Shapefile (a geospatial vector data format). The very limited datasets retrieved for the Earth Observation and Environment category are available in Excel format.

Fig. 4. Data formats used across the HVD categories.

5 Discussion

The results from the three-fold analysis are insightful according to the extant literature on HVD, availability and EDP, for that matter. Thus, vis-a-vis, the analysis at the availability pedestal, it may be inferred that Table 4 results wherein the null hypothesis of the HVDs being similar is clinched via the t-test and these results are in alignment with previous research testing for the availability-interoperability across learning management system portals [58] but not in agreement with another study seeking to understand the availability-interoperability in open source projects [53] or the availability-interoperability mismatch on account of the different standards being operative across the Industry 4.0 standards’ specifications [59]. However, these disparate findings may be attributed to the specific contexts and temporality. Thus, these results are in line with our expectations given the inherent success criterion of interoperability that the more similar and congruent the datasets, i.e., HVDs in the present study, the more the propensity for them to be interoperable thereby resulting in higher value derivation and innovation opportunities. It is worth noting that higher availability and fulfilment of technical specifications for HVDs will lead to increased interoperability on the EDP, which can ultimately bring greater value to the open data ecosystem. Interoperable datasets can enable greater ease of use and integration with other datasets, thereby improving their overall value.

6 Conclusion and Future Directions

The overall purpose of the present study was to consider three dimensions (Availability, Publisher/s, Technical specifications) of HVD in the EDP, in order to gain a better understanding of the current status and elicit potential intuitive conclusions. In a way, the study addressed the concern that: “ensuring the interoperability of data catalogues, or the creation of a pan-European data catalogue, is a big challenge faced by EU policy makers” [65: pp. 32] and this study provided a nuanced understanding of the HVD-OGDs via empirical investigation. Findings show that for the three key countries, viz., Sweden, Germany and Czech Republic, the other countries need to match the pace of the HVD publishing on the EDP. Furthermore, given the differentials in terms of the HVD structural and functional dimensions right from the provisioning of select HVD across select themes and categories and down to the metadata and other technical specifications, it is important that a benchmarking framework be adopted for deriving the actual benefits of OGD-HVD via value creation and innovation by a range of stakeholders. Finally, findings from the study hinted at the impediments towards attaining HVD linkages and the same needs to be addressed in further studies with experts’ opinions and academic insights.

The presented methodology and its results offer an opportunity to evaluate the availability of HVDs, their publishers, and technical specifications, and to improve the HVDs on the European data portal (EDP). In the future, the EDP could provide additional information on datasets, such as the number of downloads, views, and reuse of datasets, the number of showcases and use cases, the number of research projects and press articles, new dataset requests, marginal charges of datasets, internal statistics about portal usage, as well as the number of views and downloads of re-uses. This information would facilitate the efficient and effective discovery of HVDs through the EDP, eliminating the need for manual evaluation by publishers and across datasets.

Another possible future perspective which can be analyzed and considered would be the analysis of technical functionalities in the European Data Portal (or national data portals case studies) to identify needs of the data portal with respect to both the portals but also user perspective and, in this manner, proceed with the elicitation of requirements to be applied in this direction. This might be of great interest in alignment with the tension to shift towards more user-driven services offered by the open data portals.

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References

1. Public sector information directive. 2019/0024 of the European Parliament and the Council on open data and re-use of public sector information (recast) (2009). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1024/oj>
2. Zuiderwijk, A., Shinde, R., Janssen, M.: Investigating the attainment of open government data objectives: is there a mismatch between objectives and results? *Int. Rev. Adm. Sci.* **85**, 645–672 (2019)

3. REDF workshop. Types of value creation in social enterprises (2019). <https://redfworkshop.org/learn/value-creation-in-social-enterprises/>
4. Porter, M.E., Kramer, M.R.: Creating shared value. *Harv. Bus. Rev.* **89**, 62–77 (2011)
5. Benington, J.: From private choice to public value. *Public value: Theor. Pract.* **121**, 31–49 (2011)
6. Euzenat, J.: Towards a principled approach to semantic interoperability. In: *IJCAI Workshop on Ontology and Information Sharing*, Seattle, US, pp. 19–25 (2011). <https://hal.inria.fr/hal-00822909/>
7. Kalampokis E, Karamanou A, Tarabanis K. Towards interoperable open statistical data. In: *18th IFIP WG8.5 International Conference, San Benedetto Del Tronto, Italy*, pp. 180–191 (2019). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-27325-5_14
8. Kawashita, I., Baptista, A.A., Soares, D.: Open government data use by the public sector-an overview of its benefits, barriers, drivers, and enablers. *HICSS*, pp. 1–10 (2022). <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/79648>
9. Pagano, P., Candela, L., Castelli, D.: Data interoperability (2013). <https://doi.org/10.2481/dsj.GRDI-004>
10. Novakouski, M., Lewis, G.A.: Interoperability in the e-government context. *Technology Note* (2012). <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/citations/ADA611103>
11. Sheffer Correa, A., de Assis Mota, A., Toledo Moreira Mota, L., Luiz Pizzigatti Correa, P.: A fuzzy rule-based system to assess e-government technical interoperability maturity level. *Trans. Govern. People Process Policy* **8**, 335–356 (2014)
12. Guijarro, L.: Semantic interoperability in e-government initiatives. *Comput. Stand. Interfaces* **31**, 174–180 (2009)
13. Valle, P.H.D., Garces, L., Nakagawa, E.Y.: A typology of architectural strategies for interoperability. In: *Proceedings of the XIII British Symposium on Software Components, Architectures, and Reuse*, pp. 3–12 (2019)
14. Wyns, B., et al.: Good practices for identifying high value datasets and engaging with re-users: the case of public tendering data (2013). https://www.w3.org/2013/share-psi/wiki/images/3/31/Share-PSI_Submission_Paper-PwC_v0.03.pdf
15. Welle Donker, F.M., van Loenen, B.: Societal costs and benefits of high-value open government data: a case study in the Netherlands. In: *21st AGILE International Conference on Geographic Information Science: Geospatial Technologies for All*, Lund, Sweden, pp. 1–5 (2018). <http://resolver.tudelft.nl/uuid:ff6261e6-c7a6-4d4b-be4b-888acd632afb>
16. Utamachant, P., Anutariya, C.: An analysis of high-value datasets: a case study of Thailand’s open government data. In: *15th International Joint Conference on Computer Science and Software Engineering (JCSSE)*. Nakhonpathom, Thailand, pp. 1–6 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/JCSSE.2018.8457350>
17. Jetzek, T., Avital, M., Bjørn-Andersen, N.: Generating value from open government data. *ICIS 2013* (2013). <https://aisel.aisnet.org/icis2013/proceedings/GeneralISTopics/5/>
18. Benington, J., Moore, M.H.: Public value in complex and changing times (2011). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-230-36431-8_1
19. Harrison, T.M., et al.: Open government and e-government: democratic challenges from a public value perspective. In: *Proceedings of the 12th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research (dg.o 2011)*, pp. 245–253 (2011)
20. Public resource. Open data working group (2007). https://public.resource.org/open_government_meeting.html
21. Bertot, J.C., McDermott, P., Smith, T.: Measurement of open government: metrics and process. In: *45th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, Maui, HI, USA, pp. 2491–2499 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2012.658>
22. McDermott, P.: Building open government. *Gov. Inf. Q.* **27**, 401–413 (2010)

23. Reggi, L., Dawes, S.: Open government data ecosystems: linking transparency for innovation with transparency for participation and accountability. In: Scholl, H., et al. *Electronic Government. EGOV 2016. LNCS*, vol 9820. Springer, Cham (2016). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-44421-5_6
24. Peled, A.: When transparency and collaboration collide: the USA open data program. *J. Am. Soc. Inform. Sci. Technol.* **62**, 2085–2094 (2011)
25. Parycek, P., Hochtl, J., Ginner, M.: Open government data implementation evaluation. *J. Theor. Appl. Electron. Commer. Res.* **9**, 80–99 (2014)
26. Attard, J., Orlandi, F., Auer, S.: Value creation on open government data. In: 49th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS), Koloa, HI, USA, pp. 2605–2614 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2016.326>
27. Wang, V., Shepherd, D.: Exploring the extent of openness of open government data – a critique of open government datasets in the UK. *Gov. Inf. Q.* **37**, 101405 (2020)
28. Ruijter, E., Detienne, F., Baker, M., Groff, J., Meijer, A.: The politics of open government data: understanding organizational responses to pressure for more transparency. *Am. Rev. Public Admin.* **50**, 260–274 (2020)
29. Harrison, T.M., Pardo, T.A., Cook, M.: Creating open government ecosystems: a research and development agenda. *Future Internet* **4**, 900–928 (2012)
30. Linders, D., Wilson, S.C.: What is open government?: One year after the directive. In: 12th Annual International Digital Government Research Conference: Digital Government Innovation in Challenging Times, pp. 262–271 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2037556.2037599>
31. Unsworth, K., Townes, A.: Transparency, participation, cooperation: a case study evaluating Twitter as a social media interaction tool in the US open government initiative. In: 13th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research, pp. 90–96 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2307729.2307745>
32. Charalabidis, Y., Alexopoulos, C., Loukis, E.: A taxonomy of open government data research areas and topics. *J. Organ. Comput. Electron. Commer.* **26**, 41–63 (2016)
33. Kubicek, H., Cimander, R., Scholl, H.J.: Layers of interoperability. In: *Organizational Interoperability in E-Government*, Springer, Berlin (2011). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-22502-4_7
34. Charalabidis, Y., Zuiderwijk, A., Alexopoulos, C., Janssen, M., Lampoltshammer, T., Ferro, E.: Open data interoperability. In: *The World of Open Data. Public Administration and Information Technology*, Springer, Cham, vol. 28, pp. 75–93 (2018). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-90850-2_5
35. Maheshwari, D., Janssen, M.: Reconceptualizing measuring, benchmarking for improving interoperability in smart ecosystems: the effect of ubiquitous data and crowdsourcing. *Gov. Inf. Q.* **31**, S84–S92 (2014)
36. Lodato, T., French, E., Clark, J.: Open government data in the smart city: Interoperability, urban knowledge, and linking legacy systems. *J. Urban Aff.* **43**, 586–600 (2021)
37. Jimenez, C.E., Solanas, A., Falcone, F.: E-government interoperability: linking open and smart government. *Computer* **47**, 22–24 (2014)
38. Colpaert, P., et al.: Quantifying the interoperability of open government datasets. *Computer* **47**, 50–56 (2014)
39. Kalampokis, E., Karamanou, A., Tarabanis, K.: Interoperability conflicts in linked open statistical data. *Information* **10**, 249 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.3390/info10080249>
40. Maali, F., Cyganiak, R., Peristeras, V.: Enabling interoperability of government data catalogues. In: Wimmer, M.A., Chappellet, J.L., Janssen, M., Scholl, H.J. (eds.) *Electronic Government. EGOV 2010. LNCS*, vol. 6228, pp. 339–350. Springer, Berlin (2010). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-14799-9_29

41. Masoumi, H., Farahani, B., Shams Aliee, F.: Systematic and ontology-based approach to interoperable cross-domain open government data services. *Trans. Govern. People Process Policy* **16**, 110–127 (2022)
42. DiFranzo, D., et al.: TWC LOGD: a portal for linking open government data (2010). <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.13015/4607>
43. Machado, A.L., Parente de Oliveira JM. DIGO: an open data architecture for e-government. In: 15th International Enterprise Distributed Object Computing Conference Workshops, Helsinki, Finland, pp. 448–456 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1109/EDOCW.2011.34>
44. Breitman, K., et al.: Open government data in Brazil. *IEEE Intell. Syst.* **27**, 45–49 (2012)
45. Masoumi, H., Farahani, B., Aliee, F.S.: An ontology-based open data interoperability approach for cross-domain government data services. In: 25th International Computer Conference, Computer Society of Iran (CSICC), Tehran, Iran, pp. 1–8 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSICC49403.2020.9050079>
46. Ahlgren, B., Hidell, M., Ngai, E.C.H.: Internet of things for smart cities: interoperability and open data. *IEEE Internet Comput.* **20**, 52–56 (2016)
47. Buyle, R., et al.: A sustainable method for publishing interoperable open data on the data. *Data* **6**, 93 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/data6080093>
48. Washington AL. The interoperability of US Federal government information: Interoperability. *Big Data: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications* (2016). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-9840-6.ch011>
49. McKinsey global institute smart cities executive summary. Scribd 2018. <https://www.scribd.com/document/615375365/Mgi-Smart-Cities-Executive-Summary>
50. Li, W.C.Y., Nirei, M., Yamana, K.: Value of data: there’s no such thing as a free lunch in the digital economy, RIETI discussion paper (2019). <https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/value-data-theres-no-such-thing-free-lunch-digital-economy>
51. Dowdy, S., Wearden, S., Chilko, D.: *Statistics for research*. 3rd edn. Wiley-Interscience (2004)
52. Field, A.: *Discovering statistics using SPSS*. 3rd edn. Sage (2009)
53. Shamsi, F.A., Bamatraf, S., Rahwan, T., Aung, Z., Svetinovic, D.: Correlation analysis of popularity and interoperability in open source projects. In: International Conference on Innovations in Information Technology (IIT), Al Ain, United Arab Emirates, pp. 181–186 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/INNOVATIONS.2018.8605970>
54. King, H.H., et al.: Preliminary protocol for interoperable telesurgery. In: International Conference on Advanced Robotics, pp. 1–6 (2009). <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/5174711>
55. Bamoriya, P., Singh, P.: Beyond the obvious: standardization and interoperability issues in mobile banking in India. *Acta Universitatis Danubius* **6**, 14–27 (2013). <https://www.cceol.com/search/article-detail?id=564459>
56. Perumal, T., Ramli, A.R., Leong, C.Y., Samsudin K., Mansor, S.: Interoperability among heterogeneous systems in smart home environment. In: *Web-Based Information Technologies and Distributed Systems. Atlantis Ambient and Pervasive Intelligence*, Atlantis Press, vol. 2 (2010). https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-91216-32-9_7
57. DCAT. About DCAT application profile for data portals in Europe. <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/semantic-interoperability-community-semic/solution/dcat-application-profile-data-portals-europe/about>
58. Conde, M.A., Garcia-Penalvo, F.J., Piguillem, J., Casany, M.J., Alier, M.: Interoperability in eLearning contexts: Interaction between LMS and PLE. In: *Proceedings of 1st Symposium on Languages, Applications and Technologies*, Braga, pp. 205–223 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.4230/OASlsc.SLATE.2012.205>
59. Melluso, N., Grangel-Gonzalez, I., Fantoni, G.: Enhancing Industry 4.0 standards interoperability via knowledge graphs with natural language processing. *Comput. Ind.* **140**, 103676 (2022)

60. Kirstein, F., Dittwald, B., Dutkowski, S., Glikman, Y., Schimmler, S., Hauswirth, M.: Linked data in the European data portal: a comprehensive platform for applying DCAT-AP. In: Lindgren, I., et al. *Electronic Government. EGOV 2019. LNCS*, vol. 11685, pp. 192–204. Springer, Cham (2019). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-27325-5_15
61. Andrade, M.C., Cunha, R.O., Figueiredo, J., Baptista, A.A.: Do the European data portal datasets in the categories government and public sector, transport and education, culture and sport meet the data on the web best practices? *Data* **6**, 94 (2021)
62. van der Waal, S., Węcel, K., Ermilov, I., Janev, V., Milošević, U., Wainwright, M.: Lifting open data portals to the data web. In: Auer, S., Bryl, V., Tramp, S. (eds.) *Linked Open Data-Creating Knowledge Out of Interlinked Data. LNCS*, vol. 8661, pp. 175–195. Springer, Cham (2014). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-09846-3_9
63. Schuppenlehner, T., Muhar, A.: Theoretical availability versus practical accessibility: the critical role of metadata management in open data portals. *Sustainability* **10**, 545 (2018)
64. Perego, A., Cetl, V., Friis-Christensen, A., Lutz, M.: GeoDCAT-AP: representing geographic metadata by using the “DCAT application profile for data portals in Europe (2017). <https://unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/stats/documents/ece/ces/ge.58/2017/mtg3/2017-UNECE-topic-i-EC-GeoDCAT-ap-paper.pdf>
65. Ubaldi, B.: Open government data: towards empirical analysis of open government data initiatives. *OECD 2013*, vol. 22 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1787/5k46bj4f03s7-en>